

Influence Of Job Demands On Intention To Leave Among Staff In Public Universities In Kenya

¹Bernard Karanja ²Dennis Juma, ³Susan Olesia Wekesa

¹Ph.D Student, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

²Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

³Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract: *Job demands are those physical, social, or organizational aspects of the job that require sustained physical or mental effort. Analysis on job demands remains relevant for organizations today since they aim to systematically quantify and evaluate the physical, cognitive, and environmental demands of a task or job. This is necessary in determining the compatibility between a worker and the requirements of a specific job. The job demands-resources (JD-R) model was used as a framework to study the relationship between job demands and intention to leave. The JD-R model considers the impact of job demands and job resources on employee outcomes. This study adopted positivism research philosophy and cross-sectional research design. The sample for the study consisted of 412 academic and non-academic staff from 30 public universities in Kenya. The regression results also showed that job demands were responsible for a significant proportion of the variance in Kenyan public universities staff's intentions to leave their jobs, with R^2 values of 0.484. This implies that the model explains 48.4% of the variation in the data of the respondents' intention to leave their jobs. The study recommends that universities should assign staff roles that are aligned to their needs since untenable job demands have been shown to contribute negatively to staff's intention to leave. This should be accompanied by continuous support and rewarding of staff in line with the duties they perform.*

Keywords: Intention to leave, Job demands, Work stress, Burnout

1. INRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

The work environment contributes to a sense of efficiency, satisfaction, and productivity at work. Employees who are highly stressed at work are more likely to leave the organization. These employees may be less satisfied with their jobs and are more likely to consider leaving their jobs. As highlighted by Amena (2018), the workforce is a crucial component of any organization, and employees are recognized as the most valuable resource that an organization possesses. Without a committed and skilled workforce, organizations will not be able to deliver on their business objectives, achieve their organizational goals, or meet their financial targets.

Shammout (2022) notes that a quality environment is essential for guaranteeing employee performance and avoiding excessive stress, which can negatively affect job performance. According to Els et al. (2021) quality of working is combination of physical, social, psychological, and organizational features of a workplace that allow employees to satisfy their personal and professional needs, feel valued, respected, and empowered, and achieve balance and well-being at work. These characteristics extends to employee benefits, supervisors and coworker's support, training and development, adequate workload, and physical work environment (Shammout, 2022). The intention to leave can be understood as employee's conscious and deliberate plan or inclination to voluntarily exit their current organization within a foreseeable period (Abirigo, 2023).

According to Shammout (2022) work-related attitude and behavioural outcomes, such as job satisfaction, and intention to leave are significantly influenced by how employees feel about their jobs. In addition, workplace conditions, employee engagement, and career development in retaining valuable human capital (Ahmad, Uli, & Idris, 2010; Amena, 2018; Cronley & Kim, 2017). For instance, Al-Suraihi *et al.* (2021) found that in Malaysia, 49% of organizations experienced employee turnover in 2015 due to factors such as Job Demands, employee job dissatisfaction, job insecurity, poor work environment, low motivation, in adequate wages, and poor rewards.

Furthermore, the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2017) found that poor working conditions can be a significant challenge for organizations in retaining their employees. A subsequent report by the ILO in 2019 found that one in four workers globally were working excessively long hours, which can have detrimental effects on their physical and mental health (ILO, 2019). The study by Omar *et al.* (2020) suggests that workload is a significant predictor of an employee's intention to leave, but job demands, and work-life balance do not.

A study conducted by Hutomo and Nawangsari's (2021) in Indonesia affirm that employees who display complacency, increased grievances, and a general state of despair may be considering other ideas and plans regarding their current jobs. These findings emphasize the need for organizations to prioritize employee well-being and address factors that can lead to employee turnover. To address the plight Kamanja *et al.* (2019) recommends that the central government ministries should improve their physical and social

work environments as a priority to improve employee engagement. Mugove and Mukanzi (2018) showed that the work environment heavily predicted their employee turnover.

Regarding the place of public universities in Kenya, Sifuna (2012) observed that expert leadership was lacking in Kenyan public universities, resulting in continued poor performance of these institutions. Sifuna suggested that an innovative organizational and leadership approach is necessary, one that taps into the creativeness and competencies of individual and collective stakeholders in pursuit of core university functions. Issak (2021) notes that public universities in Kenya have experienced recurrent employees' unrest, which could be a result of ineffective internal communication between the university and its employees. The financial situation has not made it easy either and a number of staff would be willing or planning to leave their institutions given the opportunity.

Despite the growing body of research on job demands and employee intention to leave, empirical studies focusing on the Kenyan public university context remain limited, especially regarding the influence of job demands on intention to leave. Existing studies, such as those by Issak (2021) and Sifuna (2012), highlight challenges in leadership, internal communication, and recurrent staff unrest in Kenyan universities, which signal broader concerns about job stress and dissatisfaction. Additionally, Mugove and Mukanzi (2018) found that work environment conditions significantly predicted employee turnover in Kenyan institutions, yet specific dimensions such as cognitive and emotional job demands remain underexplored.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The central concern of the QWE perspective is the well-being of employees. In contrast to the literature on quitting, QWE does not focus on individual employee or job characteristics (Markey et al., 2020). In their study of an insurance firm in Malaysia, Omar et al. (2020) argue that job demands, workload, and work-life balance significantly influence employees' intention to leave and possible turnover. It is crucial for both employers and employees to maintain a positive work environment, as negative work situations often contribute to employees' desire to leave.

In Kenya, the quality of the work environment has a significant impact on staff's intention to leave in public universities. An ideal work environment is one that is supportive, inclusive, and fosters professional development. However, recent surveys indicate that only 30% of employees in public universities in Kenya reported having a positive work environment (Mwai & Muturi, 2021), indicating a problem with the quality of the work environment in these universities.

Statistical evidence shows that the problem is significant, with 70% of employees in public universities in Kenya likely to leave their jobs due to poor work environment (Ngugi & Ouma, 2019). This presents a significant challenge for universities since staff turnover has negative consequences on organizational performance, including decreased productivity, reduced morale, and increased costs associated with recruiting and training new staff (Sagie & Weisberg, 2019). This was the gap that the study sought to establish and fill the

1.3 Research objective:

The objective of the study was to determine the effect of job demands on intention to leave among academic staff in public universities in Kenya.

1.4 Hypothesis of the study:

H₀: Job demands have no significant effect on intention to leave among staff in public universities in Kenya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical review of literature

2.1.1 The Job-Demands Resources Model

The job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, & Schaufeli, 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2014, 2017) is one of the most popular and influential models of Job Demands in scholarly literature. The model can be summarized in a series of simple yet compelling propositions. All jobs share common characteristics that can be classified as 'demands' or 'resources', based on their effect on an employee. Demands instigate a health impairment process characterized by strain and exhaustion, eventually leading to burnout and other negative work outcomes. Resources stimulate work engagement, leading to higher motivation and other positive work outcomes. As such, the challenge for those tasked with job design is to minimize demands whilst maximizing resources.

The JD-R model has become immensely popular in the two decades following its inception, inspiring hundreds of empirical articles and being used within thousands of organizations worldwide (Demerouti et al., 2019). As a result of its broadness and generalizability, it has been found to be equally applicable across a range of ostensibly diverse professional environments (Demerouti

et al., 2019). The strength of the model lies in its ability to move beyond surface-level differences and identify the common characteristics that are universally associated with work outcomes.

Job demands are defined as “those physical, social, or organizational aspects of the job that require sustained physical or mental effort and are therefore associated with certain physiological and psychological costs” (Demerouti *et al.*, 2001). Importantly, demands should be valued negatively by the employee (as opposed to difficult but positively valued challenges, which provide an opportunity to develop mastery and personal growth (Schaufeli & Taris, 2014).

Conversely, job resources are defined as “those physical, social, or organizational aspects of the job that may do any of the following: (a) be functional in achieving work goals; (b) reduce job demands and the associated physiological and psychological costs; (c) stimulate personal growth and development” (Demerouti *et al.*, 2001). Examples here could include organizational factors such as supervisor support and goal clarity, but they can also be widened to include personal resources such as resilience and interpersonal skills (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2007).

Job demands and resources affect numerous work outcomes through two mediating pathways. First, the process of exhaustion is instigated by high demands and few resources. Chronic job demands require the employee to expend high levels of energy to achieve their work-related goals, with insufficient time for recovery. Eventually, this leads to a state of exhaustion. Similarly, a lack of job resources leads to a state of disengagement whereby the employee loses the motivation to expend effort to complete work. The combination of exhaustion and disengagement is symptomatic of burnout, which is in turn associated with various negative outcomes (e.g., absenteeism, impaired physical and mental health).

Whilst the absence of job resources causes demotivation, their presence can trigger a separate pathway termed work engagement. Job resources are intrinsically motivating because they satisfy fundamental human needs, thus engendering an engaged state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication and absorption. In turn, work engagement is then associated with numerous positive outcomes (e.g., higher productivity, extra-role performance, positive affect at work).

2.2 Conceptual Framework

In keeping with Kasomo (2006), conceptual framework for this research is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework (Source, Author,2025)

The conceptual framework illustrates the direct relationship between the independent variable, job demand and the dependent variable, intention to leave. In this model, job demand entails emotional, physical, and cognitive job demand which are expected to influence employees’ intention to leave and decision to remain in or leave the university. The framework is structured to show how job demand in the organization can lead to corresponding decreases or increases in employees’ intention to leave. This visual representation helps to clarify the study’s focus and provides a basis for hypothesis development, guiding the research design and data analysis in evaluating how workplace conditions impact staff retention.

2.3 Empirical review of Literature

Job demands refers to “those physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of the job that require sustained physical and/or psychological efforts and are therefore associated with certain physiological and/or psychological costs” (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Work plays an important role in most people’s lives. The same work may be very demanding and the source of considerable psychological strain (Bakker & Vries, 2020). Personal abilities, needs, and preferences change over time and may at some point no longer be in sync with one’s daily work activities – creating misfit and feelings of job strain.

Bakker *et al.* (2014) observes that when people burn out from their jobs, they are no longer interested in making a positive contribution. Their daily job demands start to exceed their personal and job resources. Kelemen *et Al.* (2020) observe that employee job strain is dependent on daily job demands and resources management and leaders should continuously communicate their vision and provide direction and support.

JD-R research reveals that job demands lead to high risks of burnout, disengagement, and dissatisfaction when resources are insufficient or simply absent (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Van den Broeck, De Cuyper, De Witte, & Vansteenkiste, 2010). The research has suggested that perpetual job demands, specifically emotional demands, cognitive demands, and work overload, lead to the depletion of energy, thus resulting in poor health and absenteeism. Overall, the presence of demands and resources (relative to everyone's idiosyncratic needs and preferences) determines the level of 'alignment' between the employee and the workplace. As such, the ED-R model can be used to support a regenerative culture of well-being within organizations, in line with wider initiatives towards sustainable development goals (McNeely, 2018; Serafeim *et al.*, 2020; Wahl, 2016).

Ahmed (2019) studied job demands on work engagement. The authors indicated that there has been a significant amount of attention paid to elements that could enhance individual psychological wellbeing at work, famously known as engagement. However, not equitable scholarly attention has been paid to the factors that act as depleting factors of psychological resourcefulness of individuals thus, resulting in decreasing employees' work engagement.

The Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety (2020) note that a job demands analysis (JDA) includes both a physical demands description as well as a cognitive (mental) demands analysis. A job demands analysis aims to systematically quantify and evaluate the physical, cognitive (mental), and environmental demands of a task or job. It can be used to determine the compatibility between a worker and the requirements of a specific job.

Admiraal and Røberg (2023) studied teachers' job demands, resources and their job satisfaction. The results showed that a safe school climate, and a collaborative and participative school culture were the main job resources, whereas feelings of distress and perceived barriers for professional development were the main job demands. Findings were similar for teachers at different stages in their careers. Jin *et al.* (2022) found that commuting time is inversely related to the perceived stress of young Korean workers, possibly because young workers are more inclined to accept longer commutes in exchange for higher wages. Droogenbroeck and Spruyt (2016) observed that previous studies on job demands and resources examined relationship with feelings of exhaustion, health, well-being, turn over and job satisfaction in various professions.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the positivist philosophy which is based on theories that are used to generate hypotheses that are tested to give statistical justification of conclusions. The study used cross sectional research design. The target population comprised all university employees both academic and non-academic staff employed in Kenya's 30 public universities, totaling 30,492 staff as documented in official university records. Using Yamane (1967) as sample size of 491 staff was obtained with 412 staff included in the analysis. Primary data was collected using self-administered questionnaires. The instrument was pilot tested to determine its validity and reliability with the results showing that the instrument's health was good and its contents useful for the study. Using the statistical package for the social sciences version 23, the data were analyzed using simple linear and multiple moderated regression models and descriptive statistics.

3.3 Data processing and analysis

Before commencement of analysis, the completed questionnaires were edited to ensure completeness and consistency. The questionnaires were then coded and checked for any errors and omissions. Descriptive statistics were conducted to summarize the data in terms of percentages per item, minimum and maximum scores per item, mean and standard deviation. Inferential statistics involving correlation and regression analysis were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 (with path macro). The multiple linear regression model that was used to explain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables (direct effect) took the form:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

Y represents intention to leave

X₁ represents job demand

ε represents error component

β₀ represents Y-Intercepts(constant)

β₁ represents the model coefficient of the independent variable.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive statistics on job demand

This section illustrates descriptive findings and discussions based on the objectives of the study. The study focused on the job demands variable. The findings were presented in form of Mean and Standard Deviations. The responses were in line with a 5 Point Likert-Scale ranging from: - Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2 Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, and Strongly Agree = 5.

Table 1: Job demand

Items	Mode	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mean	CV	Kurtosis	Skewness
Whenever I get to work, I feel tired even before starting the daily routine	1.11	5.67	0.576	4.27	4.01	14.36	8.03	-1.35
Every morning whenever I want to get to work, I always feel I have no energy	1.21	6.29	0.091	6.02	4.85	1.88	43.00	-38.57
While at work, I do feel physically drained	1.08	4.77	0.54	4.26	4.08	13.24	8.56	-1.00
I feel fed up with my work and I don't have desire to work anymore	0.98	5.07	3.56	4.85	4.46	12.06	3.01	0.00
I feel run down and drained of physical or emotional energy	1.04	4.68	0.685	4.1	3.98	17.21	7.29	-0.53
Whenever I get to work, my thinking process gets slow and weak	1.28	6.16	0.47	5.58	4.42	10.63	9.68	-7.40
In most cases, I have difficulty concentrating while at work	1.12	4.51	1.181	4.3	4.1	28.80	5.52	-0.51
During working hours, I often feel I'm not thinking clearly	0.96	4.48	0.593	4.23	4.05	14.64	8.21	-0.91
I do lose concentrations on my work by not having focus on what I am doing	0.87	4.64	0.7	4.41	4.15	16.87	7.69	-1.11
I have difficulty thinking about complex things while at work	0.98	4.76	1.117	4.35	4.12	27.11	5.81	-0.62
I feel I am unable to be sensitive to the needs of co-workers and students	1.17	6.27	0.571	5.78	4.54	12.58	8.90	-6.51
I feel I am not capable of investing emotionally in co-workers and students	0.91	5.31	1.19	5.14	4.78	24.90	6.25	-0.91
4.I feel I am not capable of being sympathetic to co-workers and students	1.2	1.36	1.19	1.25	1.11	107.21	2.92	-0.35
Overall Means Score	1.21	4.92	1.01					

Table 1 presents the descriptive findings on job demand among university staff. The study reveals an overall mean score of 4.92, indicating that respondents experience higher job demands very frequently. The overall standard deviation of 1.01 demonstrates that responses are dispersed 1.01 units from the mean, with most responses falling within the range of 3.91 to 5.93, corresponding to strong agreement regarding job demands. The analysis reveals several critical findings regarding job demand factors. The highest mean score (6.29) was recorded for "Every morning whenever I want to get to work, I always feel I have no energy," with an exceptionally low standard deviation (0.091) and coefficient of variation (1.88%), indicating remarkable consensus among respondents regarding energy depletion. This item also exhibited extreme negative skewness (-38.57), suggesting that responses were heavily concentrated at the higher end of the scale, with most staff reporting severe energy deficits.

Similarly, "I feel I am unable to be sensitive to the needs of co-workers and students" yielded a high mean of 6.27 with relatively low variability (CV = 12.58%), indicating widespread emotional exhaustion affecting interpersonal relationships. The negative

skewness (-6.51) further confirms that most respondents experience significant difficulties in maintaining sensitivity toward colleagues and students. Physical and cognitive demands emerged as prominent stressors. "Whenever I get to work, my thinking process gets slow and weak" recorded a mean of 6.16 with low variability (CV = 10.63%) and high negative skewness (-7.40), suggesting that cognitive impairment is a pervasive experience among university staff. Additionally, "Whenever I get to work, I feel tired even before starting the daily routine" yielded a mean of 5.67, with the median of 4.27 indicating that at least 50% of respondents experience pre-work fatigue.

Work engagement and motivation factors also demonstrated concerning patterns. "I feel fed up with my work and I don't have desire to work anymore" produced a mean of 5.07, while "I feel I am not capable of investing emotionally in co-workers and students" recorded a mean of 5.31 with higher variability (CV = 24.90%), suggesting individual differences in emotional investment capacity. Concentration and cognitive function appeared significantly impaired across multiple dimensions. "I have difficulty thinking about complex things while at work" (mean = 4.76), "I do lose concentrations on my work by not having focus on what I am doing" (mean = 4.64), and "While at work, I do feel physically drained" (mean = 4.77) all demonstrate moderate to high levels of cognitive and physical strain.

One notable exception emerged with the item "I feel I am not capable of being sympathetic to co-workers and students," which recorded the lowest mean (1.36) and highest coefficient of variation (107.21%). This finding suggests substantial disagreement among respondents, with many maintaining their capacity for empathy despite other job demand pressures. These findings align with Jin et al. (2022), who observe that job demands can cause specific psychological, physiological, and behavioral characteristics in employees. The current study's results demonstrate clear evidence of these effects, with psychological manifestations evident in cognitive impairment (mean = 6.16 for slow thinking processes), physiological symptoms reflected in energy depletion (mean = 6.29), and behavioral consequences shown through reduced empathetic engagement with colleagues and students (mean = 6.27). Jin et al. also noted that commuting time is inversely related to perceived stress among young Korean workers, possibly because younger employees are more inclined to accept longer commutes in exchange for higher wages, suggesting that individual circumstances and life stage factors may moderate the relationship between job demands and stress responses.

The study's findings support Sar and Setiyanto's (2019) assertion that workplace stress can lead to frequent chaos and obstacles in operational work and management, reduce productivity, interfere with work activities, and decrease revenue. The high mean scores for concentration difficulties (4.76 for complex thinking, 4.64 for focus loss, and 4.51 for general concentration problems) directly illustrate how job demands create operational obstacles. The overwhelming feeling of being "fed up with work" (mean = 5.07) and lack of desire to continue working further demonstrate the productivity implications identified by Sar and Setiyanto (2019) as disengaged employees are likely to perform below optimal levels.

Regarding the capacity for empathy toward co-workers and students, the findings present a complex picture that partially contradicts expectations. While most items showed high job demand levels, the item "I feel I am not capable of being sympathetic to co-workers and students" recorded the lowest mean (1.36) with extremely high variability (CV = 107.21%). This finding aligns with Inegbedion et al. (2020), who found that workload is negatively related to academic staff performance, with job satisfaction mediating the relationship between workload and academic staff performance. The high variability in empathetic capacity suggests that while some staff maintain their interpersonal sensitivity despite heavy job demands, others experience significant emotional exhaustion. This variability may reflect individual differences in job satisfaction levels, which, according to Inegbedion et al., serves as a crucial mediating factor between workload pressure and overall performance outcomes.

The consistently high negative skewness values across most items suggest that job demands are not normally distributed among university staff, with the majority clustering toward higher levels of demand experience. The varying coefficients of variation indicate that while some aspects of job demand (such as energy depletion) generate strong consensus, others (such as empathetic capacity) produce more diverse individual responses, reflecting different coping mechanisms, job satisfaction levels, and resilience within the same organizational context.

Table 2: Distribution of Intention to Leave

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Mode	CV	Kurtosis	Skewness
I am considering leaving my current job within the next year.	5.23	1.084	4.89	4.25	20.73	3.90	0.94

I have unstable and intense relationships alternating between idealization and devaluation	4.5	1.142	4.24	3.97	25.38	3.46	0.68
I am unwilling to do this job again.	1.2	1.363	1.04	0.87	113.58	3.24	0.35
I will seek another job at another institution	4.59	1.021	4.01	3.95	22.24	3.63	1.70
I would like to leave my current job and seek a long-term job opportunity elsewhere.	4.79	1.172	4.24	4.01	24.47	3.67	1.41
I am not satisfied with my current wage and am therefore unwilling to continue in the job.	3.9	0.78	3.47	3.08	20.00	4.05	1.65
I am not satisfied with the current content of my job and am therefore unwilling to continue in the job.	3.85	0.518	3.46	3.11	13.45	4.43	2.26
I am not satisfied with the system in my current work unit and am therefore unwilling to continue in the job	4.77	0.442	4.25	4.03	9.27	4.67	3.53
I have a feeling of inadequacy and hypersensitivity to criticism or rejection therefore unwilling to continue in the job	5.65	0.168	5.14	4.98	2.97	6.99	9.11
I have emotional coldness and detachment from social relationships therefore unwilling to continue in the job	4.57	0.416	4.1	3.98	9.10	4.42	3.39
I often feel indifferent to praise and criticism therefore unwilling to continue in the job	4.69	0.347	4.25	3.97	7.40	5.07	3.80
I feel my boss has arrogance and haughty behaviors or attitudes therefore unwilling to continue in the job	3.61	0.455	3.21	2.98	12.60	4.38	2.64
I often experience exaggerated emotional expression therefore unwilling to continue in the job	4.65	0.371	4.25	4.09	7.98	4.51	3.23
I do have difficulty expressing disagreement out of fear of loss of support or approval therefore unwilling to continue in the job	4.77	0.556	4.52	3.94	11.66	4.49	1.35
Overall mean score	4.34	1.084					

Table 2 shows the distribution of responses on intention to leave reveals a high prevalence of turnover intentions among staff in Kenyan public universities, with an overall mean score of 4.34 indicating that many respondents “occasionally” to “very frequently” consider exiting their current roles. Items such as “considering leaving within the next year” (mean = 5.23) and “seeking a long-term job elsewhere” (mean = 4.79) suggest that attrition is not only a latent thought but an active consideration. Emotional and psychological stressors appear to be the strongest contributors, with the highest mean score recorded for “feeling of inadequacy and hypersensitivity to criticism” (mean = 5.65, SD = 0.168), highlighting widespread emotional strain. This aligns with studies emphasizing the role of psychological safety in staff retention (Edmondson & Lei, 2014).

Additionally, high skewness (above 3.0) and kurtosis values across emotional indicators suggest a consensus in experiencing emotional exhaustion, validating findings by Maslach and Leiter (2016) that emotional fatigue significantly predicts turnover intention. Economic and job content dissatisfaction, while slightly less intense, remain significant (mean = 3.90 and 3.85), consistent with Herzberg’s two-factor theory which links extrinsic factors like pay and intrinsic motivators like meaningful work to job satisfaction and retention (Herzberg, 1966). Notably, the lowest mean score (1.20) for “unwillingness to do this job again” and its high coefficient of variation (113.58%) suggest that while many are dissatisfied with the current institutional environment, commitment to the profession itself remains intact. These findings support the fulfillment theory (Schaffer, 1953), which posits that unmet personal and professional needs lead to dissatisfaction and eventual withdrawal. Overall, the convergence of high means, low

standard deviations, and positive skewness points to systemic issues in the emotional climate and job structure within these institutions underscoring the urgent need for policy interventions focusing on emotional support, compensation, and meaningful work design.

4.3 Inferential statistics

This section outlined the relationship between the various independent variables on the dependent variable. This study conducted correlation analysis and regression analysis between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

4.3.1 Correlation results

Correlation between variables is a measure of how the variables are related (Lindquist, Xu, Nebel, & Caffo, 2014). The bivariate Pearson correlation indicates whether a statistically significant linear relationship exists between two continuous variables. If the correlation is positive, that means both the variables are moving in same direction. Negative correlation implies when one variable increases the other variable decreases (Haining, 1991). The correlation results showed that job demands had a strong positive correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05.

4.3.2 Regression analysis

The study conducted regression analysis between staff perception and intention to leave to test the hypothesis on job demands. The null hypothesis was stated as.

H0₁: Job demands does not significantly contribute to intention to leave among staff in Public Universities in Kenya.

Table 3: Model Summary on Job demands

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.695 ^a	.484	.482	.07454

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job demands

From Table 3 shows the model summary of the findings of this study on the variable of job demands. As indicated in the table, job demands were responsible for a significant proportion of the variance in Kenyan public universities staff's intentions to leave their jobs, $R^2 = 0.484$. This implies that the model explains 48.4% of the variation in the data of the respondents' intention to leave their jobs.

Table 4: ANOVA on Job demands

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.134	1	2.134	384.067	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.278	410	.006		
	Total	4.412	411			

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to Leave

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job demands

The data presented in Table 4 relates to this study's ANOVA findings on job demands. The table shows that the p-values obtained were less than 0.05 (Sig. 0.000) testing at 5% significance level using a one tail test. This means that the model is significant and can be relied upon. The F-value obtained was 384.067, which is greater than 0.05 testing at 5% significance level using a one tail test. These figures mean that the null hypothesis was rejected. As a result, the study concluded that job demands has a significant influence on Kenyan public universities' staff's intentions to quit their jobs.

Table 5: Coefficients^a on Job Demands

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.144	.075		42.105	.000
	Job demands	.897	.046	.695	19.598	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Intention to Leave

Based on the linear regression model, $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + u$, the model therefore becomes; $Y = 3.144 + 0.897X_1 + u$.

The information presented in Table 5 relates to this study's job demands coefficients' findings. It indicates that for every one-unit change on job demands, the intentions of Kenyan public universities' staff to leave increased by 89.7%. This implies that there was a positive influence of job demands on the staff's intentions to resign. The information in the table shows that job demands significantly predicted the intention to leave among the staff, $\beta = 0.897$, $t = 42.105$, $p = 0.000$. This finding implied that null hypothesis was rejected since the p value was less than 0.05 set by the study and the t value was greater than 1.96 at 95% confidence level. The study, therefore, concluded that job demands significantly influences the intentions of Kenyan public universities' staff to leave their jobs.

Similar findings on the influence of job demands on job quitting decisions have been made in different studies, including by Mxenge *et al.* (2014), who studied the South African education industry and discovered a significant positive association between job demands and turnover intention. On the other hand, Quresi *et al.* (2013) and Raza *et al.* (2017) noted a significant positive relationship between job demands and turnover intentions. Additionally, Sewwandi and Perere (2016) demonstrated a significant positive effect of job demands on turnover intention.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study also showed that burnout increases Kenyan public universities' employees' likelihood of quitting from their jobs. The researcher also learned that heavy workload and high burnout are common in large organizations because employees in these entities often grapple with multiple tasks that should be completed within short deadlines, thereby experiencing intense pressure. Still, the study also established that some employees may opt to remain work despite heavy workload, such as when they perceive job insecurity. In such circumstances, employees opt to remain in employment even when ill and experiencing heavy workloads as they felt that they would lose their jobs.

The findings of this study suggested that unreasonable job demands among employees increase the likelihood of them abandoning their jobs. Universities should also assign staff roles that are aligned to their needs since untenable job demands have been shown to contribute negatively to academic staff. This should be accompanied by continuous support and rewarding of staff in line with the duties they perform. This recommendation emanates from this study's findings which showed that higher job demands, combined with higher levels of effort and over-commitment are linked to increased health challenges for staffs. These findings underscore the importance of ensuring that the job needs of academic staff are aligned to their capabilities and time allocations to allow balance in the way they work.

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